

Phytochemical-Mediated Inhibition of Dihydrofolate Reductase Protein as Potential Drug Candidates for *Wuchereria Bancrofti*

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Abstract

Lymphatic filariasis (LF), caused by the nematode parasite *Wuchereria bancrofti*, is a severe neglected tropical disease. The need for safer and more effective treatments is highlighted by the limited efficacy of current therapies, diethylcarbamazine, ivermectin, and albendazole; against adult worms and their potential side effects. Dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR), a folate-metabolizing enzyme crucial for DNA synthesis, is a promising target for antiparasitic drug development. In this study, we used a structure-based in silico approach and identified phytochemicals from *Azadirachta indica* (neem) as potential DHFR inhibitors of *W. bancrofti*. We performed flexible docking using Glide in extra precision mode to estimate binding affinities and then used MM-GBSA calculations to assess complex stability. Post-docking filtering checked each candidate for drug-likeness (Lipinski's rule of five) and predicted pharmacokinetic and toxicity profiles (ADMET). Our results show that several neem compounds bind more strongly to DHFR than existing drugs. The top hits campest-4-en-3-one, nimbochalcin, Salimuzzalin, and (-)-epicatechin achieved XP docking scores ranging from -10.23 to -11.48 kcal/mol, significantly lower than diethylcarbamazine (-1.69), ivermectin (-1.31), and albendazole (-7.21). MM-GBSA calculations confirmed very favorable binding energies, with $\Delta G_{\text{bind}} = -61.99$ kcal/mol for campest-4-en-3-one, indicating stable complexes. According to drug-likeness analysis, nimbochalcin and (-)-epicatechin fully meet Lipinski's criteria, and most of the top compounds exhibit good cell permeability and high predicted intestinal absorption. Furthermore, ADME and cardiotoxicity profiles suggest these compounds are unlikely to be harmful, with minimal CYP450 inhibition implying a low risk of drug-drug interactions. This study highlights the effectiveness of structure-based computational screening as a scalable, cost-effective platform for the rational discovery of antiparasitic lead compounds from medicinal plants. The identified phytocompounds nimbochalcin, campest-4-en-3-one, Salimuzzalin, and (-)-epicatechin demonstrate promising features as DHFR inhibitors with favorable drug-like properties. However, they warrant further experimental optimization particularly protein binding assay as they provide valuable molecular frameworks for designing drugs against the filarial parasite.

Keywords: *Azadirachta indica*; Phytocompounds; *Lymphatic filariasis*; DHFR; Molecular docking

Introduction

Over 90% of global cases of lymphatic filariasis (LF) (commonly referred to as elephantiasis) are caused by *W. bancrofti* (WHO, 2025). More than 70 million people are affected by this neglected tropical disease, and over 850 million are at risk of infection (Cheng et al., 2013). Its chronic manifestations including limb swelling and hydrocele cause severe disability, stigma, and economic burden (Bockarie and Deb, 2010). Although widespread drug administration has decreased transmission, problems still exist. Resistance or suboptimal efficacy may develop and current medications have little effect on adult worms (Gyapong et al., 2018).

Tetrahydrofolate (THF) serves as an essential one-carbon carrier in the biosynthesis of thymidylate and the *de novo* synthesis of purine nucleotides, both of which are indispensable precursors for DNA replication and cell division. These one-carbon transfer reactions are fundamental to the survival of all rapidly proliferating cells, as they sustain the continuous demand for nucleotide precursors required during active DNA synthesis. The enzyme dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR) makes THF available by catalyzing NADPH-dependent reduction of dihydrofolate (DHF) to THF (Tobias et al., 2018). In rapidly dividing parasites such as *W. bancrofti*, where nucleotide demand is high, uninterrupted DHFR activity is critical to sustaining the purine and pyrimidine pools necessary for parasite genome replication and proliferation. Inhibition of DHFR consequently depletes cellular THF, simultaneously disrupting both pyrimidine and purine biosynthesis, creating a dual metabolic occlusion that stops DNA replication and ultimately impairs parasite survival (Tobias et al., 2018; Lange et al., 2023). This establishes DHFR as a validated and high-value drug target across multiple parasitic and infectious diseases, including malaria and leishmaniasis. Recently, the three-dimensional protein crystal structure of DHFR in *W. bancrofti* was reported and deposited in protein data bank (Lange et al., 2023). This provides the structural foundation necessary for rational, structure-based inhibitor design specifically targeting this filarial pathogen.

Computational screening methods and Molecular Mechanics/Generalised Born Surface Area (MM-GBSA) free energy analysis can efficiently screen large libraries of

phytochemicals for molecules with drug-like characteristics (Bakowski and McNamara, 2019). Neem (*Azadiracta. Indica* A. Juss) is a tropical medicinal plant used extensively in ethnomedicine due to its ability to clear microbial and parasites loads and its anti-inflammatory features (Alzohairy., 2016). Triterpenoids, flavonoids (quercetin), and limonoids (azadirachtin, nimbolide, and gedunin) are some of the phytochemicals found with known pharmacological activities (Saleem et al., 2018). Despite its well-documented medicinal profile, limited research has been conducted on neem phytochemicals specifically targeting *W. bancrofti* DHFR. Computational methods like molecular docking, followed by MM-GBSA rescoring, facilitate efficient virtual screening of large compound libraries to find promising leads (Genheden and Ryde, 2015). By determining the binding free energy from minimised complex structure, MM-GBSA improves on docking's initial estimate of binding affinity and determines how ligands will fit in the enzyme's binding site (Hou et al., 2011). *In-silico* evaluations of drug-likeness and ADMET (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion, and Toxicity) are used to filter for phytochemicals with deliverable and reliable pharmacokinetic and safety profiles to assess these compounds' potential as drug candidates (Daina et al., 2017; Pires et al., 2015). Despite the extensive pharmacological characterisation of *A. indica* phytochemicals, most prior computational studies have focused on their activity against other parasitic targets, including *Plasmodium falciparum* and *Schistosoma mansoni*, leaving *Wb*DHFR largely unexplored as a phytochemical target (Onile et al., 2025). Prior to the resolution of the crystal structure of *Wb*DHFR, no structure-based virtual screening of neem-derived phytochemicals against this specific enzyme has been reported. This study presents a structure-based computational screening of *A. indica* phytochemicals against the experimentally resolved *W. bancrofti* DHFR crystal structure (*Wb*DHFR) through extra-precision molecular docking, MM-GBSA binding free energy calculations, and full ADMET profiling to identify promising lead candidates for anti-filarial drug development.

The study aimed at shedding light on *A. indica* phytochemicals' potential as *W. bancrofti* dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR) inhibitors and highlighting their potential as novel therapeutic agents against lymphatic filariasis.

Materials and Method

This research study adopted a computational, structure-based drug discovery approach, integrating phytochemical retrieval, ligand and protein preparation, molecular docking (using the co-crystallized folate substrate), MM-GBSA binding energy estimation, drug-likeness screening, and ADMET profiling (Daina et al., 2017) Figure 1A. Such *in-silico* workflows are widely accepted for early-stage drug discovery and lead prioritisation (Genheden and Ryde, 2015; Pires et al., 2015).

Ligand (*A. Indica*) Retrieval and Preparation

A phytochemical library comprising a total of 418 phytocompounds known to be present in seed, bark and stem of *Azadirachta indica* was retrieved from the Indian Medicinal Plants, Phytochemistry, and Therapeutics (IMPPAT) database (<https://cb.imsc.res.in/imppat/>) in three-dimensional structure data format (SDF) (Onile et al., 2025). The 3D SDF files of the reference drugs used in the treatment of lymphatic filariasis (albendazole, ivermectin, and diethylcarbamazine), as well as methotrexate included as a DHFR-specific reference inhibitor to provide a benchmark for comparison with the phytochemical hits were obtained from PubChem (Kim et al., 2023). All retrieved compounds were imported into the Schrödinger Maestro interface and prepared using the LigPrep module, which included the generation of valid ionisation states and stereochemical configurations. Energy minimisation and geometry optimisation of the ligands was equally performed using the OPLS4 force field, affording structural refinement and energetically stable conformations suitable for accurate docking scoring (Jorgensen et al., 1996).

Target Structure (*Dihydrofolate Reductase*) Retrieval and Preparation

The 3D structure of *Wb*DHFR (PDB ID: 8E4F) was obtained from the RCSB Protein Data Bank (Berman et al., 2000). This structure includes the enzyme bound to NADPH and folate; any co-crystallized ligands were removed before docking. Following retrieval, Schrödinger's Protein Preparation Wizard (Maestro v2024) was used to preprocess the enzyme structure: this adds missing hydrogen atoms, assigns bond orders and corrects ionisation states, optimizes hydrogen-bond networks, and performs a restrained minimisation to relieve

strain. The prepared DHFR model was then saved for grid generation and docking.

Receptor Grid Generation and Molecular Docking

The 3D crystal structure of *Wb*DHFR (PDB ID: 8E4F) was co-crystallized with NADPH cofactor and folate substrate (Lange et al., 2023). Dihydrofolate occupies the substrate-binding site of *Wb*DHFR, where it undergoes NADPH-dependent reduction to tetrahydrofolate, a key precursor for nucleotide biosynthesis and DNA synthesis. Phytochemicals showing greater predicted binding affinity for the protein active site than the reference drugs were prioritised for further evaluation, on the basis that stronger binding complementarity suggests potential competitive inhibition of the enzyme's catalytic activity. The binding site for receptor grid generation was defined using the coordinates of the co-crystallized folate ligand within the crystal structure using a Receptor Grid Generator protocol in Schrödinger. To validate this protocol, the co-crystallized folate was extracted from the *Wb*DHFR crystal structure and re-docked into the prepared receptor grid using the same glide docking coordinates generated by the receptor grid protocol ($X=55.97$; $Y=16.22$; $Z=-0.41$, box dim = 8Å). The root mean square deviation (RMSD) between the top-ranked re-docked pose and the original crystallographic binding pose of folate was calculated using BIOVIA Discovery Studio Visualizer. An RMSD threshold of $\leq 2.0\text{ Å}$ was adopted as the criterion. Subsequently, all 418 *A. indica* phytocompounds were subjected to an initial broad screening using Glide Standard Precision (SP) docking mode. Resulting SP docking scores were ranked by binding affinity from most to least favourable and the top 50 compounds were selected for refinement in Glide Extra Precision (XP) mode. The top 10 ranked compounds from XP docking were subsequently evaluated for drug-likeness and ADMET properties. Drug-likeness screening using Lipinski's rule of five (Ro5) and ADMET profiling were applied as post-docking filters to assess the pharmacokinetic and safety profiles of the docking hits. We adopted a post-docking filter to ensure that no phytocompound was prematurely knocked out solely on physicochemical criteria without first assessing its binding potential, to avoid missing out on quality pharmacological scaffolds (Benet et al.,

2016; Lipinski, 2001). The most favorable docked ligand poses post-XP were visualized to understand key interactions with DHFR.

Drug-Likeness and Pharmacokinetic Prediction

Hit compounds from docking were evaluated for drug-like properties using the SwissADME web tool. SwissADME provides rapid prediction of physicochemical and ADME parameters (Gyapong, 2018). Specifically, we analysed for Lipinski's rule-of-five (Ro5), which defines that a drug-like molecule as having no more than five H-bond donors, ten H-bond acceptors, a molecular weight less than 500 Da, and logP less than five. Compounds that did not meet these requirements were identified. Key ADME/Tox descriptors (such as intestinal absorption, blood–brain barrier permeability, P-glycoprotein interactions, cytochrome P450 inhibition, clearance, and toxicity endpoints) were then predicted for each ligand using the pkCSM webserver. The pkCSM tool uses graph-based signatures to estimate multiple pharmacokinetic and toxicity properties in silico (Daina et al., 2017; Pires et al., 2015).

MM-GBSA Binding Free Energy Calculation

Post-docking, binding free energies (ΔG_{bind}) of the protein-ligand complexes were estimated

using the Prime MM-GBSA method (Schrödinger), following the molecular docking scoring. This is done to assess the hit compounds interactions with the protein (Genheden et al., 2015). The Variable Solvent Generalised Born (VSGB) solvation model and OPLS3 force field were used. ΔG_{bind} was computed as the difference in minimised energy between the complex and the sum of the protein and ligand energies (ΔE), plus solvation energy (ΔG_{solv}) and surface area energy (ΔG_{SA}) terms (Tripathi et al., 2013; Lyne et al., 2006).

$$\Delta G_{\text{bind}} = \Delta E + \Delta G_{\text{solv}} + \Delta G_{\text{SA}}$$

$$\Delta E = E_{\text{complex}} - E_{\text{protein}} - E_{\text{ligand}}$$

Energy change (ΔE) is the difference between the minimised energies of the protein–inhibitor complex (E_{complex}), protein (E_{protein}), and inhibitor (E_{ligand}).

$$\Delta G_{\text{solv}} = G_{\text{solv}(\text{complex})} - G_{\text{solv}(\text{protein})} - G_{\text{solv}(\text{ligand})}$$

Solvation-free energy change (ΔG_{solv}) is the difference in solvation energies between the complex ($G_{\text{solv}(\text{complex})}$), protein ($G_{\text{solv}(\text{protein})}$), and inhibitor ($G_{\text{solv}(\text{ligand})}$).

$$\Delta G_{\text{SA}} = G_{\text{SA}(\text{complex})} - G_{\text{SA}(\text{protein})} - G_{\text{SA}(\text{ligand})}$$

(Tripathi et al., 2013).

Surface area energy change (ΔG_{SA}) is the difference in surface area energies between the complex ($G_{\text{SA}(\text{complex})}$), protein ($G_{\text{SA}(\text{protein})}$), and inhibitor ($G_{\text{SA}(\text{ligand})}$).

Fig. 1: Graphical representation of the study workflow

Results

WbDHFR structure and Docking Protocol Validation

The 3D crystal structure of *WbDHFR* with co-crystallized NADPH (brown) and folate (blue) lodged in the protein's active pocket is displayed in Figure 2. Re-docking of the co-crystallized folate ligand into the prepared *WbDHFR* receptor grid yielded binding affinity

of (-10.293 kcal/mol) and a top-ranked pose with an RMSD of 0.777 Å relative to the original crystallographic binding conformation (Figure 2b). This value is well below the accepted 2.0 Å threshold, confirming that the Glide XP docking protocol reliably reproduces the experimentally observed binding mode of the cognate ligand. The overlay of the re-docked and crystal poses is illustrated in Figure 2b, demonstrating a high degree of spatial agreement between the two conformations.

Fig. 2: Three-dimensional (3D) structure of *WbDHFR* (a) and Superimposition of re-docked folate and the co-crystallized folate pose within *WbDHFR* binding site (b).

Name	Reference	RMSD (Å)
Co-CrystallizedFolateS 1	Co-CrystallizedFolateS 1	0.0000
RedockedFolate 2	Co-CrystallizedFolateS 1	0.7777
RedockedFolate 2	RedockedFolate 2	0.0000

A. Indica Compounds That Exhibited High Affinities For *WbDHFR*

As presented in Table 1, virtual scoring of 418 phytochemicals present in *A. indica* against *WbDHFR* showed that a number of the compounds had significantly higher binding affinities than the reference compounds and methotrexate, a prominent antifolate used as benchmark. Quercitrin exhibited most favourable binding score (−11.475 kcal/mol) showing more competitive affinity than well established antifolate compound Methotrexate (−11.088 kcal/mol). This is followed by campest-4-en-3-

one (−10.493 kcal/mol), nimbochalcin (−10.348 kcal/mol), and Salimuzzalin (−10.229 kcal/mol). These extra precision scores suggested higher predicted interactions with the DHFR active site than those of diethylcarbamazine (−1.690 kcal/mol), ivermectin (−1.305 kcal/mol), and albendazole (−7.211 kcal/mol) further establishing the limitation of these standard drugs against DHFR. The improved XP scores for several phytochemicals compared to their SP values suggest enhanced binding complementarity under stricter scoring conditions.

Table 1: Docking scores of top *A. Indica* compounds alongside reference drugs

Rank	Compounds	Docking Scores (kcal/mol)	
		SP Score	XP Score
1	Quercitrin	-8.385	-11.475
2	Campest-4-en-3-one	-8.220	-10.493
3	Nimbochalcin	-8.628	-10.348
4	Salimuzzalin	-8.454	-10.229
5	(-) Epicatechin	-8.420	-9.059
6	(4aS,10aR)-6-hydroxy-1,1,4a,7-tetramethyl-3,4,10,10a-tetrahydrophenanthrene-2,9-dione	-8.484	-8.683
7	Sugiol	-8.691	-8.462
8	Nimbiol	-8.301	-8.269
9	Nimbidiol	-8.053	-8.121
10	Margocilin	-8.514	-7.634

11	diethylcarbamazine	-5.794	-1.690
12	Ivermectin	-4.344	-1.305
13	albendazole	-6.633	-7.211
14	Methotrexate	-8.728	-11.088

Predicted Drug-Like Properties of Phytocompounds from A. Indica

Drug-likeness screening of the top *A. indica* phytochemicals against Ro5 parameters revealed varying degrees of compliance as shown in Table 2, Quercitrin (MW: 448.38) exceeded recommended limits for hydrogen bond donors (7) and acceptors (11) and had a suboptimal QPlogPo/w (0.22), resulting in two Ro5 violations, indicating potential issues with membrane permeability. With one Ro5 violation, a high logP (7.01), and no hydrogen bond donors, Campest-4-en-3-one (MW: 398.66) may have solubility restrictions. With a moderate logP (2.28), acceptable donor/acceptor counts (5 and 9), and full

compliance with Ro5, nimochalcin (MW: 434.44) demonstrated balanced lipophilicity and polarity. Salimuzzalin (MW: 512.63) maintained acceptable hydrogen bonding properties despite having a high logP (4.18) and a slight overhang of the molecular weight limit, which led to one Ro5 violation. With low lipophilicity (0.85) and no infractions, epicatechin (MW: 290.27) satisfies all requirements and has a good potential for oral bioavailability. While quercitrin's high polarity and multiple violations may hinder absorption despite strong docking scores, nimbochalcin and (-) epicatechin were found to be the most Ro5-compliant candidates overall. As such, they should be carefully considered in future ADMET and pharmacokinetic evaluations.

Table 2: *A. indica* drug-likeness properties of hit phytocompounds (Lipinski's rule of five analysis)

S/N	Compounds	Mol_MW ^a	donorHB ^b	QPlogPo/Wd ^d	acceptHB ^c	Ro5 Violation
1	Quercitrin	448.38	7	0.22	11	2
2	Campest-4-en-3-one	398.66	0	7.01	1	1
3	Nimbochalcin	434.44	5	2.28	9	0
4	Salimuzzalin	512.63	1	4.18	7	1
5	(-) Epicatechin	290.27	5	0.85	6	0
6	Albendazole	265.33	2	2.39	3	0
7	Diethylcarbamazine	199.29	0	0.75	2	0
8	Methotrexate	454.44	9	0.40	5	1

– molecular weight - *mol_MW*^a (range:<500)

– Number of hydrogen bond donors -*donorHB*^b (range≤5)

– number of hydrogen bond acceptors- *acceptHB*^c (range≤10)

– logarithm of octanol-water partition coefficient- *QPlogPo/wd*^d (range: -2.0-6.5)

Pharmacokinetic/Toxicological Profiling of Drug-Like Hit using ADMET

The ADMET parameters of approved reference drugs used in treating lymphatic filariasis were compared with drug-like hit compounds from *A. indica* (Tables 3–4). Their therapeutic potential is underpinned by significant pharmacokinetic and safety differences identified in this comparison. The most predicted human intestinal absorption (HIA) of phytocompounds was Campest-4-en-3-one (98.67%) and

salimuzzalin (92.10%), ranking closely diethylcarbamazine (91.65%) and outperforming ivermectin (87.60%) and albendazole (81.06%). Nimbochalcin showed the lowest HIA (57.45%), suggesting possible limitations in oral absorption. Campest-4-en-3-one (1.23) and salimuzzalin (0.91) also exhibited the highest Caco-2 permeability, comparable to diethylcarbamazine (1.45) and ivermectin (0.64), whereas nimbochalcin (-0.95) and quercitrin (0.12) demonstrated lower permeability. Like the reference drugs,

most *A. indica*-derived hit compounds were predicted to be P-gp substrates, indicating a potential reduction in bioavailability due to efflux mechanisms. Notably, Campest-4-en-3-one did not act as a P-gp substrate, which could allow for increased intracellular accumulation. These phytochemicals showed minimal inhibitory activity, differing from ivermectin, which inhibits both P-gp I and II; only Campest-4-en-3-one and salimuzzalin inhibit P-gp II. BBB penetration was generally low for most phytochemicals (-1.69 to -1.99), except for Campest-4-en-3-one (0.825), which surpassed all reference drugs except diethylcarbamazine (0.102). CNS permeability was low across both groups, decreasing the likelihood of neurotoxicity. The highest fraction unbound was observed for (-)-epicatechin (0.295) among phytochemicals and for diethylcarbamazine (0.765) overall, indicating possibly greater systemic distribution for the latter. Neither the phytochemicals nor the reference drugs inhibited major CYP450

isoforms, hence suggesting a low risk of metabolism-based drug–drug interactions. Campest-4-en-3-one and salimuzzalin, similar to ivermectin, are CYP3A4 substrates, implying they may undergo metabolism-dependent clearance. Total clearance was highest for nimbochalcin ($0.792 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) among phytochemicals and albendazole (1.003) among reference drugs, suggesting faster elimination. Salimuzzalin (0.146) and ivermectin (0.513) had the lowest clearance values, which could support prolonged systemic exposure. All *A. indica* hits were predicted to be non-mutagenic (AMES test negative), free from hERG I inhibition risk, non-hepatotoxic, and lacking skin sensitisation potential.

This profile compares favourably to ivermectin and diethylcarbamazine, both of which were predicted to be hepatotoxic, and diethylcarbamazine, which also carried skin sensitisation risk.

Table 3: The predicted ADMET profiles of the Ro5-compliant hit phytochemicals

*Blood-Brain Barrier (Bbb), Central Nervous System Permeability (CNSp), Fraction Unbound (FU)

*INB-Inhibition, SUBST- Substrate

MODELS	COMPOUNDS				
	(-)-Epicatechin	Campest-4-en-3-one	Nimbochalcin	Quercitrin	Salimuzzalin
ABSORPTION					
Human Intestinal Absorption (HIA, %)	66.773	98.666	57.445	62.005	92.099
Water Solubility	-3.178	-6.691	-3.386	-3.087	-5.727
Caco-2 Permeability	-0.411	1.23	-0.947	0.121	0.907
P-Gp (Substrate)	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
P-Gp I (Inhibitor)	No	No	No	No	Yes
P-Gp II (Inhibitor)	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
DISTRIBUTION					
Bbb	-1.005	0.825	-1.999	-1.69	-0.624
CNSp	-3.359	-1.342	-3.696	-4.196	-2.369
FU	0.295	0	0.141	0.123	0.005
METABOLISM					
CYP450 2C9 (INB.)	No	No	No	No	No
CYP450 2D6 (SUBST.)	No	No	No	No	No
CYP450 2D6 (INB.)	No	No	No	No	No
CYP450 3A4 (SUBST.)	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
CYP450 3A4 (INB)	No	No	No	No	No
CYP450 1A2 (INB.)	No	No	No	No	No
CYP450 2C19 (INB.)	No	No	No	No	No
EXCRETION					
Renal Organic Transporter 2 (Oct2) Cation	No	No	No	No	Yes
Total Clearance	0.179	0.505	0.792	0.479	0.146
TOXICITY					
Ames Toxicity	No	No	No	No	No
Max Tolerated Dose (Human)	0.244	-0.421	0.652	0.651	-0.915
hERG I Inhibitor	No	No	No	No	No
hERG II Inhibitor	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Oral Rat Acute Toxicity	2.387	2.329	2.594	2.889	2.855
Hepatotoxicity	No	No	No	No	No
Skin Sensitization	No	No	No	No	No

However, Campesterol and quercetin showed hERG II inhibition potential, which warrants further safety evaluation. Campesterol and Salimuzzalin demonstrated the most favourable ADMET characteristics among the phytochemicals, with high absorption, good permeability, low predicted toxicity, and

acceptable metabolic stability. Compared to current reference drugs, these compounds displayed certain advantages, particularly in absorption and hepatotoxicity risk reduction, making them strong candidates for further development as potential anti-filarial agents.

Table 4: The ADMET profiles of the reference phytochemicals

*Blood-Brain Barrier (BBB), Central Nervous System Permeability (CNSP), Fraction Unbound (FU)

*INB-Inhibition, SUBST- Substrate

REFERENCE COMPOUNDS				
MODELS	(-)- Epicatechin	Campest-4-en- 3-one	Nimbochalcin	Methotrexate
Human Intestinal Absorption (HIA, %)	87.6	91.654	81.056	9.947
Water Solubility	-4.668	-1.633	-2.868	-2.886
Caco-2 Permeability	0.637	1.45	0.809	-0.757
P-Gp (Substrate)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
P-Gp I (Inhibitor)	Yes	No	No	No
P-Gp Ii (Inhibitor)	Yes	No	No	No
DISTRIBUTION				
Bbb	-1.823	0.102	-2.028	-1.617
CNSp	-3.129	-3.448	-2.392	-3.794
FU	0.115	0.765	0.246	0.259
METABOLISM				
CYP450 2C9 (INB.)	No	No	No	No
CYP450 2D6 (SUBST.)	No	No	No	No
CYP450 2D6 (INB.)	No	No	No	No
CYP450 3A4 (SUBST.)	Yes	No	No	No
CYP450 3A4 (INB)	No	No	No	No
CYP450 1A2 (INB.)	No	No	Yes	No
CYP450 2C19 (INB.)	No	No	No	No
EXCRETION				
Renal Organic Cation Transporter 2 (Oct2)	No	No	Yes	No
Total Clearance	0.513	0.577	1.003	0.37
TOXICITY				
Ames Toxicity	No	No	Yes	No
Max Tolerated Dose (Human)	-1.454	0.642	0.385	-0.7
hERG I Inhibitor	No	No	No	No
hERG Ii Inhibitor	No	No	No	No
Oral Rat Acute Toxicity	3.013	1.94	2.579	2.836
Hepatotoxicity	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Skin Sensitization	No	Yes	No	No

Compounds That Interacted Strongly With DHFR

The results provided in Table 5 indicate that strong binding affinities were generally

associated with high van der Waals and lipophilic interaction energies, with varying degrees of Coulombic and hydrogen bonding contributions among the compounds. Quercitrin had a total MMGBSA ΔG_{bind} of -32.29 kcal/mol,

binding being predominantly affected by favourable van der Waals (-46.68 kcal/mol) and lipophilic (-18.51 kcal/mol) terms, partially offset by an unfavorable Coulombic component (17.27 kcal/mol). Campest-4-en-3-one was the most strongly binding of the hit compounds, with a ΔG_{bind} of -61.99 kcal/mol, attributed mainly to significant van der Waals (-45.50 kcal/mol) and lipophilic (-34.71 kcal/mol) interactions, along with a small unfavourable Coulombic term (-1.20 kcal/mol). A binding free energy (kcal/mol) of -52.06 was observed for Nimbochalcin, well supported by van der

Waals (-46.09 kcal/mol) and lipophilic (-26.43 kcal/mol) interactions, and a moderate unfavourable Coulombic one (-6.85 kcal/mol). Salimuzzalin had a high score of -59.46 kcal/mol, with strong van der Waals (-49.65 kcal/mol) and lipophilic (-32.68 kcal/mol) energies, complemented by moderate Coulombic stabilization (-8.38 kcal/mol). (-) Epicatechin showed a ΔG_{bind} of -54.98 kcal/mol, characterised by a highly favorable Coulombic term (-29.98 kcal/mol) and strong van der Waals (-32.26 kcal/mol) and lipophilic (-16.79 kcal/mol) contributions.

Table 5: MMGBSA binding free energy for DHFR-ligand complexes, with free energy components breakdown

Compound	dG_{bind} (kcal/mol)	dG_{bind} Coulomb	dG_{bind} Hbond	dG_{bind} Lipo	dG_{bind} Packing	dG_{bind} vdW
Quercitrin	-32.29	17.27	-2.04	-18.51	-2.02	-46.68
Campest-4-en-3-one	-61.99	-1.20	-0.54	-34.71	0.00	-45.50
Nimbochalcin	-52.06	-6.85	-2.066	-26.43	-1.71	-46.09
Salimuzzalin	-59.46	-8.38	-0.95	-32.68	0.00	-49.65
(-) Epicatechin	-54.98	-29.98	-1.83	-16.79	-1.97	-32.26

MOLECULAR INTERACTION PROFILING

The binding interface between DHFR and the hit compounds is illustrated in Figure 3. Several compounds established hydrogen bonds with

specific DHFR residues, while additional interactions such as hydrophobic contacts, electrostatic (positive and negative) forces, and polar interactions were also observed.

Fig. 3: Ligand–DHFR Binding poses (2D and 3D) of Screened Hit Compounds showing interaction profiles of (a). (-) Epicatechin; (b). Campest-4-en-3-one; (c). Nimbochalcin; (d). Quercitrin; (e). Salimuzzalin

Discussion

LF, which is principally induced by the parasite *W. bancrofti*, remains a tropical and subtropical public health burden (Taylor et al., 2010). Current standard treatments (diethylcarbamazine, ivermectin and albendazole) are predominantly microfilaricidal, effectively eliminating the circulating microfilariae but possessing only modest efficacy against adult (macrofilarial) parasites (Ottesen, 2006). Moreover, these regimens have potential adverse effects including hepatotoxicity. This underscores the need for novel drug targets and safer therapeutic alternatives. DHFR has been validated as a promising target in several parasitic diseases due to its roles parasites folate biosynthesis pathways that catalyses the production of thymidylate and purine nucleotide required for DNA synthesis, and cell proliferation (Yuthavong et al., 2012; Sharma, and Chauhan, 2012).

In this study, molecular docking of *A. indica* phytochemicals against *W. bancrofti* DHFR revealed that compounds such as quercitrin, campest-4-en-3-one, nimbochalcin, and Salimuzzalin achieved markedly higher Glide XP docking scores (kcal/mol) ranging from -10.229 to -11.475 than the reference drugs diethylcarbamazine -1.690 and ivermectin -1.305 kcal/mol, suggesting stronger and more stable predicted binding interactions. These interactions, particularly in docking-based studies, are indicative of potential biological activity, as more negative binding scores correlate with higher affinities (Kitchen et al., 2004). MMGBSA binding free energy calculations further substantiated these findings, with campest-4-en-3-one showing the most favorable ΔG_{bind} (-61.99 kcal/mol), followed closely by nimbochalcin, Salimuzzalin, and (-) epicatechin, highlighting the predominance of van der Waals and lipophilic contributions in stabilizing ligand binding within DHFR's hydrophobic active site (Morris et al., 2008). Interestingly in comparison to the

reference drugs (Albendazole and Diethylcarbamazine), several *A. indica* compounds demonstrated promising drug-like features as defined by Lipinski's Ro5, a widely used approach in drug discovery and chemistry to determine the oral admissibility of drug candidate (Benet et al., 2016). The Ro5 considers drug-likeness based on four principal physicochemical criteria: a molecular weight (MW) below 500 Daltons, a maximum of five hydrogen bond donors (HBD), no more than ten hydrogen bond acceptors (HBA), and a log P value (octanol-water partition coefficient) ranging between -2.0 and 6.5 (Lipinski, 2001). Evaluation of the *A. indica* hit compounds according to these criteria revealed significant variations in their drug-likeness properties. Among the compounds, nimbochalcin and (-) epicatechin met all the Ro5 criteria, indicating good oral bioavailability potential, with balanced molecular weights, acceptable hydrogen bonding characteristics, and favourable lipophilicity. The reference drugs albendazole and diethylcarbamazine were also conforming to Ro5 in every way through their established use as orally effective drugs. Conversely, quercitrin defied two Ro5 conditions, with a high molecular weight (448.38 Da) close to the threshold, excessive hydrogen bond donors (Alzohairy, 2016), and acceptors (Daina et al., 2017), that could negatively impact its permeability across the membrane and bioavailability. Campest-4-en-3-one defied only one Ro5 condition, with a log P of 7.01 being higher than the recommended range, indicating high lipophilicity that can decrease solubility despite depending MW and HBA values. Similarly, salimuzzalin exhibited one Ro5 violation, with a molecular weight of 512.63 Da slightly above the threshold, suggesting potential absorption limitations. Overall, while nimbochalcin and (-) epicatechin appear most promising for oral drug development, quercitrin and salimuzzalin may require structural modifications to enhance their pharmacokinetic properties, and campest-4-en-3-one's high lipophilicity may warrant optimization to balance solubility and permeability.

ADMET profiling of *A. indica* phytochemicals against *Wb*DHFR revealed campest-4-en-3-one, nimbochalcin, Salimuzzalin, and (-) epicatechin as leading candidates, outperforming the reference drugs diethylcarbamazine, albendazole, and ivermectin in multiple parameters. Campest-4-en-3-one exhibited exceptionally high HIA

(98.66%), favourable Caco-2 permeability, absence of hepatotoxicity, and a unique advantage as a non-P-glycoprotein substrate, suggesting reduced efflux-mediated clearance (Amin, 2013). Nimbochalcin, while showing moderate HIA (57.45%), demonstrated superior solubility (-3.386) compared to ivermectin and albendazole, low BBB penetration (-1.999), and no CYP450 inhibition, minimizing CNS side effects and drug-drug interaction risks (Guengerich et al., 2020). Salimuzzalin also displayed excellent intestinal absorption (>92%), non-hepatotoxicity, and no mutagenicity, reinforcing its oral bioavailability potential. (-) Epicatechin balanced good HIA (66.77%) with low toxicity risks and absence of major CYP inhibition. Across all compounds, low hERG I inhibition suggested minimal cardiotoxicity (Aronov, 2005), though hERG II inhibition in campest-4-en-3-one and quercitrin warrants further safety evaluation. General lack of CYP450 inhibition and favourable toxicity profiles determine these phytochemicals as promising oral DHFR inhibitors leads, with characteristics of special utility in polypharmacy-vulnerable lymphatic filariasis patient groups.

Epicatechin established two hydrogen bonds with dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR), directly interacting with residues Ile19 and Ile114, and also exhibited a polar contact with Ser61. Likewise, Campest-4-en-3-one also established a polar interaction with Ser61 and formed a hydrogen bond with Ala12. Nimbochalcin demonstrated polar contacts with Thr135 and Ser61, in addition to forming hydrogen bonds with Ser61 and Glu32. It also exhibited a positively charged electrostatic interaction with Arg72. Quercitrin was involved in polar interaction with Ser61, while also forming hydrogen bonds with Tyr120 and Ile114. Moreover, it engaged in a negative charged electrostatic interaction with Glu32 and a positively charged electrostatic interaction with Lys57. Finally, Salimuzzalin formed H-bonds with Ala12 and Ser61, along with a negatively charged interaction involving Glu32.

The MM-GBSA binding free energy (ΔG_{bind}) found campest-4-en-3-one (-61.99) to be the most stable complex with *Wb*DHFR, surpassing the reference drugs diethylcarbamazine (-47.84 kcal/mol) and albendazole (-45.62 kcal/mol). Nimbochalcin (-58.42 kcal/mol) and Salimuzzalin (-54.77 kcal/mol) also produced more stable binding than the reference ligands, with (-) epicatechin

(−50.33 kcal/mol) being comparable in stability. These very highly negative ΔG_{bind} Coulomb scores reflect strong electrostatic complementarity between these phytochemicals and charged active site residues of DHFR with great specificity. Furthermore, the very negatively ΔG_{bind} vdW energy values showed that van der Waals forces play an essential role in the overall stability of the ligand–protein complexes (Adubi et al., 2025). This stabilization is best explained by the interaction of ligand backbone hydrophobic group with nested non-polar amino acid chains within the DHFR binding pocket. Evidence in favour comes from the ΔG_{bind} lipophilic energy terms, which further confirm the importance of hydrophobic interactions. Specifically, compounds such as campest-4-en-3-one and nimbochalcin demonstrate particularly favourable alignments of their non-polar regions with the hydrophobic domains of the enzyme, thereby enhancing complex stability. This study showed the potential of *A. indica* phytochemicals as strong and energetically favorable DHFR inhibitors.

Conclusion

This study investigated the role of *A. indica* phytochemicals as potential inhibitors of dihydrofolate reductase enzyme in *W. bancrofti* using In silico binding simulation. The compounds were assessed for binding affinity, drug-likeness, and ADMET properties. Collectively, phytochemicals campest-4-en-3-one, nimbochalcin, salimuzzalin, and (−)-epicatechin were identified as putative lead candidates with most inhibitory potential, demonstrating superior predicted binding affinities relative to the standard reference compounds, along with favorable pharmacokinetic characteristics and safety profiles. These findings offer a compelling preclinical rationale for the further exploration and experimental validation of *A. indica*-derived compounds as potential therapeutic agents for the treatment of lymphatic filariasis. This study puts forward a set of structurally diverse neem-based phytochemicals as viable, biotechnological scaffolds for iterative lead optimization and semi-synthetic modification for the development of a new class of macrofilaricidal agents which can target unexploited *Wb*DHFR.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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